

FEDERATED DATA NETWORKS

Overview

Pediatric clinical research is currently constrained by limited access to comprehensive, high quality, real-world data. This issue is especially pressing in the case of rare and complex diseases, where small patient populations are distributed across multiple countries. Traditional data-sharing models face increasing legal and logistical challenges, particularly under strict data protection regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Federated Data Networks (FDNs) offer a compelling solution to this challenge, enabling cross-border and cross-institutional research collaboration while preserving data privacy and institutional control.

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The Challenge: Fragmented Pediatric Data Limits Progress

In pediatric healthcare, the rarity and complexity of many diseases means that there are only a **small number of patients per country**, limiting research, therapy development, and the ability to improve patient outcomes. Moreover, the availability of real-world data for newer and often expensive therapies remains scarce, **making it difficult for Health Technology Assessment (HTA) bodies to properly evaluate new therapies**. The absence of large, diverse datasets also hampers collaboration with the MedTech industry and innovation ecosystems, which increasingly depend on artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning to advance diagnostics and treatment.

With many countries having only one or two specialized children's hospitals, benchmarking care and evaluating systems performance is also challenging.

The Solution: Federated Data Networks

Federated Data Access provides a method for analyzing sensitive data without physically transferring it across national or institutional boundaries (**Figure 1**). This approach is particularly relevant in the context of GDPR and other data protection frameworks, as it allows **data to remain under the control of its owner** while still enabling collaborative analysis.

Federated Data Networks (FDNs) are actively applied in pediatric research, with PHEMS serving as a clear example through initiatives like cardiology benchmarking, AI-based sepsis prediction in pediatric intensive care units, and personalized treatment for hemophilia. These use cases highlight how **collaborative analytics can enhance healthcare outcomes while preserving data privacy**.

Figure 1. Federated Data.

In a non-federated system, authorized users access full datasets directly within a secure workspace. In contrast, federated data access allows users to search for relevant datasets using metadata. Then, instead of accessing the data themselves, users send a request for a remote task, which is reviewed by data controllers. Once approved, the task is run on the data and the aggregated results are shared with the user in a secure workspace.

Technical Infrastructure and Standards

The success of a federated approach depends on the adoption of common technical and data standards. In PHEMS, this means that a data user access data in multiple hospital through a federated network, with **all databases aligned to a common data language model (OMOP)**.

A central component of this ecosystem is the **Federated Node (FN)**, a tool designed to enable federated analytics based on the open Common Application Programming Interface (API). The FN itself is not a full product, but a modular component that integrates with other systems such as metadata catalogs, user interfaces for task submission, and dashboards for viewing results. It incorporates technologies such as Keycloak for token and identity management, Nginx as a reverse proxy, and Kubernetes for scalable deployment. A PostgreSQL database is used to manage user credentials and task-related information.

Existing and Future Applications

FDNs are currently used in the Data Analysis, and Real World Interrogation Network (**DARWIN EU**), to provide evidence on the use, safety and effecti-

venes of medicines in humans to the European Medicines Agency. FDNs are also a complementary approach to the current plan for secondary data sharing under the **European Health Data Space (EHDS)**.

Key Takeaways

Federated Data Networks (FDNs) are a practical, privacy-preserving solution for collaborative pediatric research, especially in rare and complex diseases where data is inherently fragmented.

FDNs comply with data protection laws like GDPR by allowing data to remain under the control of the original data holder while enabling powerful, distributed analysis.

Capacity to support technical infrastructure, like Federated Nodes, and data harmonization (e.g., OMOP CDM) are essential to success.

Real-world applications in sepsis prediction, cardiology benchmarking, and hemophilia treatment demonstrate FDNs' potential to enhance patient outcomes while preserving privacy.